

Useful information

Date: 6th June 2025

Venue: Centre for Research and Technology Hellas

Address: [Εθνικό Κέντρο Έρευνας & Τεχνολογικής Ανάπτυξης ΕΚΕΤΑ-CERTH](#)

Meeting Room : Central building, Library

Registration

[📄 STEERS M2.3 June 6th Hackathon - registration form](#)

Link to EeLP:

<https://elixir.mf.uni-lj.si/course/view.php?id=116>

Aim of the workshop

Conduct hands-on evaluation of the RSQ Indicators prioritised during the first workshop, providing feedback on their utility and ease of implementation, as well as concrete examples of their application.

The Hackathon also includes participation from WP4 - T4.3 - with a training session on survey preparation for software development training.

Joint slide deck here: [📄 ELIXIR-STEERS M2.3 Workshop & Hackathon.pptx](#)

Hackathon slides start at #25

Collected [📄 RSQI indicators](#) on Wednesday 4th June 2025 during

[📄 ELIXIR-STEERS WP2 workshop on research software management quality indicators](#)

List of usage of indicators: [📄 D2.3 Implementation of selected RSQ indicators](#)

Time (CET)	Subject
09:00	Sign in, collect guidelines document on indicators to be discussed
09:05	Summing up of AHM workshop outcomes (Karel Berka) Collected RSQI indicators
09:15	Flash talks: Community use cases Scipion (Lola Sanchez) Mol* (Radka Svobodová) Proteomics data analysis workflows (Veit Schwämmle) Two pipelines from the biodiversity community (Solenne Correard; remote) CAID (Gabor Erdos) Single-Cell RNA-Seq Data Analytics (Georgios Gavriilidis / Anastasios Oulas)
09:30	STEERS WP3 Technical matrix intro (Jose Ma Fernández/Anna Golobardes) ELIXIR-STEERS M3.3 report
09:45	Working session - implementation of selected RSQ indicators D2.3 Implementation of selected RSQ indicators
11:00	Coffee break
11:30	WP2 - WP4.3 Training session: Survey preparation for software development training (Brane Leskošek, Nazeefa Fatima)
12:00	Working session continued D2.3 Implementation of selected RSQ indicators
13:30	Feedback from working session; discuss next steps
14:00	Closing and light lunch
15:00	Depart

Notes on Indicators

Karel Berka intro: AI selection of indicators
 Curated Research Software Quality Indicators Gemini

AI perspectives - Three perspectives: Researcher/Funder/Infrastructure - STEERS probably focuses on Researcher and Infrastructure perspectives; less on Funders (?)

From Veit's flash talks - can workflows have SMPs? Something to be considered by SMP group

Workshop work:**📌 D2.3 Implementation of selected RSQ indicators**

Add indicators to DSW so upon filling up the software management plan, the Indicators will fill in.

Use OpenEBench to keep metrics on software as well to keep metrics on indicators as well

Complex software pieces depend direct or indirectly on other libraries and components, which could have incompatible licences with the main one, with the research institution policy or among themselves

What should be software quality metrics of a workflow/software/tool with mixed quality parts/dependencies?

- It should get the Lowest score of each indicator based on all dependencies? Or maybe it is not applicable?
- It also depends on whether the component is part of the backbone or an optional dependency (for instance a conditional branch)
- Maybe a warning not to use weird quality dependencies? Use at your own risk!

Indicators - DSW

- Description of indicators need to be polished as some of them can't be used as is.
- Are we putting the indicators inside the DSW KM?
 - If yes, do we add or modify questions/answers to align with the indicators?
- To provide feedback on the Knowledge Model, information :
📄 ELIXIR-STEERS T3.2 - SMP Content Feedback
- Important to bring to the Knowledge Model the potential new items from the spreadsheet: **📌 D2.3 Implementation of selected RSQ indicators**
- Can the implemented Knowledge Model be then served back to the communities for trial and feedback?
- <https://openebench.bsc.es/observatory/FAIRness>
Let's follow-up how to combine OPEN E-Bench FAIRness score (assessment) and compatibility with DSW SMP.
- Use DSW to prepare/update the Github repository from the filled in SMP (preseed it)
 - **📄 ELIXIR-AHM-2025_DSW-SMP-Workshop_final.pptx**

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ChatGPT/Gemini did good job on improving the indicator description - maybe we can use it on all indicators at the end to improve the description

- Maybe we should run over them all - and also to try to provide also a possible metric

And maybe we can try to make coding LLM to make judgement assessment based on Github

- But previous tests did not worked yet very well

Maturity model of Indicators

- Connected with use cases to help support their adoption (like more citations, less breaks)
- Level - Critical, Good, Great - bars to reach the installation possibility on HPC, e.g.

Function indicators are nice and philosophical, but how to assess that

- Test against ground truth - CASP-like
- But hard to assess if not
- Make it highly optional -
- "It works as advertised"

It can get problematic e.g. with health-related data

How to get from the "scripting for myself" to publicly shared code for use by others?

WP2 - WP4.3 Training section

Survey on **assessment of training needs (training skills) in software development**. The objectives of the survey are:

1. identify topics that are needed to “develop skills” in software development - confirm the training needs identified in the workshop
2. gather what are training needs from the Nodes
3. identify Nodes that have these trainings
4. identify Nodes that need these trainings

What are the topics you think training is essential in a context of Software Development?

- **Fundamental training**
 - e.g. Version Control, data visualisation
- **Advanced/Special training**
 - e.g. Training around specific tools for Data Analysis

What are the special training skills (for instructors) that you think are essential to deliver training in software development?

Rank: Rank from 1 (not very important) to 5 (essential).

Topic	Type	Rank	Comments
Compatibility	Advanced	3	This software can be used on other systems. Examples of risks involved in connecting different software and how to address them.
FAIRness			See Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
Findability	Advanced	2	Where are people looking for software? What are Software registries and examples of them? What are different types of repositories for publishing software source code and

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			<p>release artefacts? What are Persistent Identifiers (PID), which are useful for software? How to enable citations of your software so that others can find it?</p>
Accessibility	Fundamental	4	<p>What Publicly Accessible Repositories are available and what to consider when selecting one for publishing software artefacts, source code distribution etc? What to consider when making software Open source and what tools are available to support it? Packaging</p>
Interoperability	Fundamental	4	<p>Defining interfaces and validation of inputs and outputs, Using free / common format, standards</p> <p>What are common file formats and interfaces for different types of software? (Perhaps also complex data type definitions, considerations for usage patterns such as piping in linux etc...)</p> <p>Where will this software be placed in a workflow? (expected</p>

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			<p>input/output)</p> <p>Safe integration Single intrinsic metadata file</p>
(Re)Usability	Fundamental	5	<p>Facilitate software applicability, containerisation And on top, reproducibility of the results</p> <p>What to consider when selecting a programming language? (Skills, future proofing, integration) What is software maintenance and what are examples of approaches suitable to different types of projects? What is usability and how to test for it?</p>
Community			<p>See interoperability How to find and align with community standards? How to collaborate and invite contributions to software projects? (Such as using collaborative version control platforms, community building...) What are the different types of Scientific Standards and how to adopt and contribute to them? What to consider when selecting a standard?</p>

Contribution	Advanced		<p>Assuming that this is about issue tracking</p> <p>Why keeping track of when changes were made and by whom is important? How to set up and use a version control system? Why and how to review code and changes to the software?</p>
Documentation	fundamental		<p>Standards and best practices (https://developer.wordpress.org/coding-standards/inline-documentation-standards/php/)</p>
Licensing	Fundamental		<p>Overview of basic licenses and examples, with a focus on reuse of the software</p>
Security	Fundamental & Advanced		<p>VI+RF> some security basics (no password hard coded in the code...) KB+BL> Connected with the source code Automatic testing for security as well?</p>
Source code	fundamental		<p>KB+BL: Are there any standards on HOW to write the code? Best practises</p>
Sustainability	Fundamental (from a code perspective) & advanced (from a product perspective)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Whether there is a community, modularity of the code • Keeping older

			<p>workable versions of the software</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (JMF) Hooking software releases with Zenodo publications • (JMF) Registering the software repository into SoftwareHeritage
Testing	Fundamental & advanced		<p>VI+RB> there is a need for basics of other items before one can delve into testing. KB+BL> Types of tests and how to set them up</p>
Versioning & Issue Tracking	Fundamental		<p>KB+BL></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1] to know WHY to use versioning 2] recipes HOW to use versioning with different services e.g. GitHub ... <p>Git basics and mentions of standards</p>
Monitoring	Advanced	1	<p>Monitoring of the service - does it ping? Does it work?</p>

Notes on teaching (collectively taken)

Keywords

Classes have to have keyword

Which teaching materials correspond to the different categories / dimensions

At least two levels - fundamental (terminology), more advanced (certain tools)

organisation:

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One course - some fundamentals in detail + advanced one only as awareness levels

Or Learning path - individual topics.

In that case, a common slide representing the complete learning path could be shown at the beginning of every individual course to remind the context of the course within the path (big goal).

Github lesson - as a modules

But it needs also some “big goal” lesson that would connect them

Indicators - some software has not filled all indicators, but the question is whether is missing the **skill** or the **motivation**?

Combine skills with training materials -

Skills for audience -

E.g. licencing - more legal, application to the licences, but

Class descriptions>

Requirement

Goals

Objectives

Outcomes

Identify the topics above - what is still missing?

How to assess RSQ and how to get it to the higher level